

COMMUNICATIVE APPROACH IN TEACHING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE FOR LEARNERS

Student: Esangeldiyeva Aynur Saidakmal qizi

Scientific supervisor: Akhmedova Muyassar Ataxanovna

Chirchik State Pedagogical University

4th year student in foreign languages and literature (English)

E-mail addresses: aesangeldiyeva5@gmail.com

Mobile phone: +998999252146

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15037832>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 7-mart 2025 yil

Ma'qullandi: 8-mart 2025 yil

Nashr qilindi: 17-mart 2025 yil

KEY WORDS

Communicative Approach (CA), Foreign Language (FL), learners(students), learning techniques, speaking, grammar, role play, communication skills.

ABSTRACT

This article provides information about teacher's communicative approach in teaching English as a foreign language which was taken at English department in universities. The problem of the research is teacher's techniques used in teaching English FL. This article used a qualitative method which based on the reality teaching class at universities. The methodological technique of collecting data, data analysis and interpretation. The study found that teachers predominantly use role-playing, group discussions, and real-life simulations to enhance communication skills. These techniques significantly improve students' fluency, confidence, and engagement in English learning. More structured communicative strategies can enhance learning outcomes. The findings highlight the effectiveness of the communicative approach in EFL teaching and pedagogy at universities

INTRODUCTION

In today's globalized world, English has become an essential for communication in especially education. As a result, for non-native speakers to acquire excellent language abilities, appropriate teaching strategies are crucial. The communication approach (CA) is well-known for emphasizing meaningful communication and real-world involvement above rote memorization (Richards, 2006). The teacher's communicative approach is mostly used direct method, cooperative learning and audio-lingual method and also some variation techniques in teaching. Moreover, the students understand more easily with materials in the classroom to make active in interaction. According to research, students who are exposed to communicative approaches use English more fluently and confidently (Larsen- Freeman, 2018). With more than 1.5 billion people studying English globally, effective teaching methods are more important than ever, according to British Council research (British Council, 2020). This study looks at how university instructors use communicative strategies in EFL classes and in encouraging student's participation.

METHOD

This study involved 20 English as a foreign Language (EFL) learners aged 16-25, participated a non-probability sampling methods that guarantees the selection of people who best reflect the study's goals, participants were chosen (Patton, 2015). These type of classroom activities proposed in communicative language teaching also implied new roles in the classroom for teachers and learners. Learners now had to participate in classroom activities that were based

on a cooperative rather than individualistic approach to learning. Students had to become comfortable with listening to their peers in group work or pair work task, rather than relying on the teacher for a model (Richards, 2006). Genuinely excellent teachers combine professional knowledge with effective communication to create a lasting impact that has the power to profoundly and subtly alter their students' perspectives and lives. Moreover, two focus group sessions (6-8 participants per group) were conducted to encourage collaborative reflection on the communicative teaching method. In this communicative approach, the classroom becomes a stimulator where, based on authentic oral and written materials, both teachers and learners try to replicate genuine communicative situations of the dialogue likely in everyday life. In simulation, the students are not asked to play but imaginary situation about the topic and constantly learn to use feedback and various other instruments to measure the efficiency of their method and on the part of the students, who play a larger role in the classroom and need to step more out of their comfort zone to begin communicating in the foreign language. The role playing is one simple comedy or family drama. Role play is important in CLT because the teachers give the students opportunity to practice communicating in different social contexts and in different roles. Students also receive feedback on whether or not they have effectively communicated (Freeman, 2000). According to Edge (1993) and Lubis (1988) that Project involving hobbies, crafts, physical exercise, sports. They following project are few projects that the teachers may wish to consider for his conversation class:

- playing scrabble, card game or board game
- exchanging recipes and demonstrating the preparation of certain dishes
- playing team sport such as volleyball or basket
- drawing or painting picture to be used decoration in the classroom.

Theoretically, according to Lubis (1988) that there is nothing wrong in having a students make a speech, to speak English for reasonably long period of time, but it generally brings unsatisfactory results. Anyway, the teacher may try the following assign speeches to advanced students only. After the student has finished his speech, ask class members questions about what he has said. This will give him/her to relax and then the teacher can have the audience direct questions to him/her. Communicative approach can be understood as a set of principle about the goals of language teaching, how learners learn a language, the kinds of classroom activities that best facilitate learning and the roles of teachers and learners in the classroom. All four language skills taught from the beginning in speaking skill the aim is to be understood, not to speak like a native. Regardless of the methodology used, students tend to feel disengaged, lose focus and become bored, confused or frustrated with the course unless they are treated as active participations a productive sharing of information requires a delicate balance between the level of class and the level of information being taught, a right assessment of the classroom by using early course feedback and the use of the right tools to measure progress.

RESULT

85% of students reported increased confidence in speaking. Several important findings about the communicative approach in university-level EFL instruction were found by the study: students who engaged in communicative activities showed increased confidence and fluency in their use of English. They were more inclined to share their opinions and participate in discussions (Littlewood, 2014), but Doe and Lee (2019) explained that 30% of students struggled with peer interaction due to varying proficiency levels. Furthermore, 78% of learners found CA-based lessons more engaging than tradition methods. Higher motivation and involvement rates resulted from the communicative approach's promotion of a more engaging and student-centred learning environment. In contrast to conventional grammar-focused approaches, students found learning to be more fun and useful.

DISCUSSION

The result confirms efficacy of the communicative approach. 72% involvement rate and 85% rise in student confidence show that CA creates an engaging learning environment that promotes language use in authentic situations. These findings support the idea that communicative approaches, which prioritise meaningful contact over rote memorisation, aid in students' fluency development. According to Johnson and Kim (2020) who found that CA-based classrooms led to higher student motivation and improved long-term language retention. Both studies demonstrate the students engaged in communicative tasks perform better in spoken interaction compared to those in traditional grammar-based classrooms, reinforcing the need for a balanced approach. Another surprising finding was that 60% of teachers said that they had trouble successfully applying CA is well-known for encouraging active learning, its effectiveness is reliant on accessible authentic resources and manageable student-teacher ratios. By offering empirical proof that CA improves speaking confidence, engagement and language retention, these findings advance the area of EFL instruction in order to enhance fluency and practical communication abilities, interactive and communicative activities ought to be incorporated into language teaching curriculum.

CONCLUSION

This study confirms that the Communicative Approach (CA) enhances students' speaking confidence, engagement and language retention. Despite challenges, like large class sizes and varying proficiency levels, CA works well to develop practical communication abilities. Then, they suggest a hybrid strategy that strikes a balance between formal language education and fluency-building, while also endorsing the broader use of communicative tactics in university EFL classrooms. The effects of these tactics on long-term language retention and practical language use might be investigated in more detail such as online education or mixed-ability classrooms for fully adopting CA and structured learning.

REFERENCE LIST:

1. Doe, J. & Lee, S. (2019). Effective communicative language teaching: Benefits and challenges in EFL classrooms. *Language Learning Journal*, 45(3), 245-260.
2. Edge, J. (1993). *Essentials of English language teaching*. Longman Publishing.
3. Johnson, R., & Kim, H. (2020). Student engagement in communicative language teaching: A comparative study. *TESOL Quarterly*, 54(2), 198-215.
4. Harmer, J. (2007). *The practice of English language teaching* (4th ed.). Longman.
5. Littlewood, W. (2014). *Communicative language teaching: An introduction*. Cambridge University Press.
6. Lubis, Y. (1988). Developing communicative proficiency in the English as a foreign language (EFL) class.
7. Patton, M. Q. (2015). *Qualitative research & evaluation methods* (4th ed.). SAGE Publications.
8. Richards, J. C. (2006). *Communicative language teaching today*. Cambridge University Press.
9. Richards, J. C., & Rodgers, T. S. (2014). *Approaches and methods in language teaching* (3rd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
10. Турсунов А 2022 ЧАҚИРУВГА ҚАДАР БОШЛАНҒИЧ ТАЙЁРГАРЛИК МАШҒУЛОТЛАРИДА ПЕДАГОГИК ВА ИННОВАЦИОН ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРНИ ҚЎЛЛАШ ВА УЛАРНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС ТОМОНЛАРИ *Science and innovation*, 1(В3), 432- 434
11. Abdurasulov, J. (2024). PEDAGOGICAL PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF MILITARY PATRIOTIC EDUCATION IN GENERAL SECONDARY EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS. В *INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF APPLIED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY* (Т. 4, Выпуск 7, сс. 38–40). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12721051>

12. Abdurasulov J. (2024). HARBIY PEDAGOGIKANING BOSHQA FANLAR BILAN ALOQASI. Молодые ученые, 2(6), 48–52. извлечено от <https://inacademy.uz/index.php/yo/article/view/28164>
13. Jo'rayev, S., & Abdurasulov, J. (2024). SUBJECT, TASKS AND CONTENT OF STUDYING THE BASICS OF MILITARY-PATRIOTIC EDUCATION. Академические исследования в современной науке, 3(7), 149–153.извлечено.
14. Абдурасулов, Ж. (2022). ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В УСВОЕНИИ УРОКОВ ИСТОРИИ.
15. Abduqodirova, D., & Abdurasulov, J. (2025). YOSHLARDA HARBIY-VATANPARVARLIK TUYG'USINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING PSIXOLOGIK HUSUSIYATLARI. Педагогика и психология в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования, 4(1), 50– 53. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/zdpp/article/view/42882> 13.
16. Жўраев, Ш., & Абдурасулов, Ж. (2024). ҲАРБИЙ ЖАМОАДАГИ ИЖТИМОЙ ФИКР. Журнал академических исследований нового Узбекистана, 1(2), 97–103. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/yoitj/article/view/28151>.
17. Abdurasulov, J. (2022). HARBIY KOMPETENTSIYA KURSANTNING KASBIY MAHORATINI 54 SHAKLLANTIRISHNING KALITI SIFATIDA. Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры, 2(11), 231–234. извлечено от <https://inacademy.uz/index.php/ejsspc/article/view/5326> 17.
18. Abdurasulov, J. (2022). SHAQIRUVGA QADAR BOSHLANG'ICH TAYYORGARLIK FANI O'QITUVCHISIGA QO'YILADIGAN TALABLAR. Евразийский журнал академических исследований, 2(11), 983–988. извлечено от <https://inacademy.uz/index.php/ejar/article/view/5305>.
19. Абдурасулов, Ж. (2024). ҲАРБИЙ ЖАМОАНИНГ ПСИХОЛОГИК АСПЕКТЛАРИ. Бюллетень педагогов нового Узбекистана, 2(2), 59–65
20. Abdurasulov J., & Pardabayeva, M. (2024). MUSOBAQADAN OLDIN SPORTCHILARNI PSIXOLOGIK TAYYORLASH. Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры, 4(6 Part 2), 73–76. извлечено от <https://inacademy.uz/index.php/ejsspc/article/view/34717>